

Development and validation for determination of nirmatrelvir in pharmaceutical formulation using UV-visible spectrophotometry

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Abstract

The objective of the present work was development and validation of Nirmatrelvir by UV-visible spectroscopy as per ICH guidelines. The method was performed by using methanol as a solvent and determination was absorption maxima, which was found at 226 nm. The validation parameters were optimized, and the linearity obeys Beer's law of 50 to 250 microgram/ml with a correlation coefficient of 0.999. The accuracy and precision were found to be within acceptance limits, indicating the method was found to be accurate and precise. So, the proposed method can be used for the routine analysis of drugs and formulations.

Key Words

Nirmatrelvir, UV spectrophotometer, Methanol, Method development, Validation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nirmatrelvir (Fig. 1) chemically known as (1R,2S,5S)-N-((S)-1-cyano-2-((S)-2-oxopyrrolidin-3-yl)ethyl)-3-((S)-3,3-dimethyl-2(2,2,2-trifluoroacetamido)butanoyl)-6,6-dimethyl-3-azobicyclo[3.1.0]hexane-2-carboxamide is an antiviral medication which acts as an orally active 3C-like protease inhibitor. It has a molecular weight of 499.53g/mol with molecular formula $C_{23}H_{32}F_3N_5O_4$. Nirmatrelvir is a white to pale-colored powder with practical solubility in methyl isobutyl ketone, 1-butanol, and isopropyl acetate, sparingly soluble in anisole, n-propyl acetate, n-butyl acetate, and insoluble in heptane. It has a Log P value of 2.12 and pKa 7.1. Nirmatrelvir/ritonavir, sold under the brand name, Paxlovid, is a co-packaged medication used to treat COVID-19 (1).

Fig. 1: Chemical structure of Nirmatrelvir

As per the literature survey, it was known that analytical methods were developed for estimation of Nirmatrelvir in pharmaceutical formulations. The developed methods included HPLC methods and LC-MS/MS method for the quantification of Nirmatrelvir in bulk drugs (2-4). But it was evident that no UV spectrophotometric method was developed to estimate Nirmatrelvir in pharmaceutical formulation. Hence, the present study aimed to develop and validate for the determination of Nirmatrelvir by using UV Spectrophotometer.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and Chemicals

Nirmatrelvir working standard was obtained as sample from the Simson Pharma Limited, Mumbai. All the solvents used for the development of method were procured from Merck, Mumbai, India. And all the chemicals utilized for the development of method were of AR grade purchased from sigma Aldrich, Bangalore, India.

Instruments

T60V UV/VIS double beam spectrophotometer with 1cm matched quartz cuvettes was used for the estimation of Nirmatrelvir in pharmaceutical formulations. All the parameters were controlled by UV win software. Other instruments utilized in the study included weighing digital balance, ultrasonic bath sonicator.

Preparation of standard and sample solution

An accurately weighed 10 mg of Nirmatrelvir working standard was made to dissolve in 10 ml of Methanol solvent constituting to a concentration of 1000 µg/ml. 1 ml of this stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water (concentration 100 µg/ml). 1 ml of the above solution was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water to obtain a concentration of 10 µg/ml.

20 tablets were accurately weighed, and an average weight was calculated. Weight equivalent to 10 mg of Nirmatrelvir was made to dissolve in 10 ml of Methanol solvent. The stock solution was subjected to sonication using an ultrasonic bath sonicator for 30 mins. Later the solution was filtered and 1ml of filtrate was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. Finally, 1 ml of the above solution was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water.

Method Validation (5)

Linearity

The linearity of this method was determined by preparing a serial dilution in the concentration ranges of 50-250 µg/ml and their absorbance was measured. A graph was plotted between concentration and absorbance values.

Precision

% relative standard deviation (%RSD) was calculated by performing intra-day and inter-day precision studies. A solution with a concentration of 150 µg/ml was prepared in six replicates. Their absorbance was measured within a day (intra-day precision studies) and for two consecutive days (inter-day precision studies).

Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was determined by calculating % recovery values. Solutions in three levels 50 %, 100 %, and 150 % were prepared by standard addition method and their absorbance was noted. From these values, % recovery was calculated at three levels.

Specificity

For the determination of specificity of this method, a blank solution was prepared and observed for any interference of absorbance of solvent with Nirmatrelvir absorbance.

Limit of detection and Limit of quantification

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were calculated using standard deviation of the response and slope of the regression equation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to develop and validate a simple, novel UV spectrophotometric method for the determination of Nirmatrelvir in pharmaceutical formulations.

Initially for the development of this method, the standard drug Nirmatrelvir was subjected to solubility studies where the drug was made to dissolve in different solvents such as methanol, acetonitrile, water.

From the above solubility studies, it was found that drug was freely soluble in methanol. So, for the further study, Methanol solvent was used as diluent for the preparation of solutions.

In order to detect the wavelength for the measurement, a standard solution of concentration 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared and scanned in the UV range of 200-400 nm in UV spectrophotometer as shown in Fig. 2. Maximum absorbance was observed at a wavelength of 226nm and it was utilized for further investigation.

Fig. 2: UV spectrum of Nirmatrelvir

The prepared standard solutions and sample solutions were placed in UV spectrophotometer and their respective absorbance were measured and noted as presented in table 1.

Table 1: Optical Characteristics

S. No.	Parameters	Results
1.	Absorption maximum	226 nm
2.	Linearity range	50-250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3.	Regression equation	$y = 0.0056x + 0.0041$
4.	Slope	0.0056
5.	Intercept	0.0041
6.	Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9996
7.	Molar extinction coefficient ($\text{L}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	0.11×10^5
8.	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2\text{-}0.001$ absorbance units)	0.0058
9.	Accuracy (% recovery)	99.57 - 101.20
10.	Precision (Intra-day) % RSD (Inter-day) % RSD	0.14 0.11
11.	LOD	10.56 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
12.	LOQ	32.02 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
13.	Standard error	0.018

For the determination of linearity of the method, serial dilutions in the range 50-250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were prepared, and absorbance was measured. Later a graph was plotted by taking concentration on x-axis and absorbance values on y-axis as shown in Fig. 3 and results were summarized in Table 2. From the graph, correlation coefficient values were determined, and it was found to be 0.9996.

Fig. 3: Linearity plot of Nirmatrelvir

Table 2: Results of Linearity

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	50	0.289
2	100	0.576
3	150	0.854
4	200	1.105
5	250	1.427
Regression coefficient (r^2)		0.9993
Correlation coefficient (r)		0.9996

The %RSD for intra-day precision studies was found to be 0.14 and for inter-day precision studies it was found to be 0.12, indicating the developed method to be precise. The results for precision were presented in table 3a and 3b.

Table 3a: Intra-day precision results

Sample Name	Sample Absorbance	% Assay
1	0.854	100.38
2	0.856	100.62
3	0.855	100.50
4	0.857	100.74
5	0.854	100.38
6	0.856	100.62
Average	0.855	100.54
% RSD	0.14	0.14

Table 3b: Inter-day precision results

Sample Name	Sample Absorbance	% Assay
1	0.896	100.50
2	0.895	100.39
3	0.894	100.28
4	0.896	100.50
5	0.895	100.39
6	0.897	100.61
Average	0.896	100.45
% RSD	0.12	0.11

Accuracy of the method was determined by calculating % recovery. The % recovery was found to be 99.57 % - 100.07 % and indicates that the method was accurate. The accuracy results were summarized in table 4.

Table 4: Accuracy results

Sample No.	Spike Level (in %)	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50	5.00	5.05	100.97	101.20
2	50	5.00	5.07	101.44	
3	50	5.00	5.06	101.20	
1	100	10.00	9.97	99.69	99.57
2	100	10.00	9.94	99.46	
3	100	10.00	9.96	99.57	
1	150	15.00	14.99	99.91	100.07
2	150	15.00	15.03	100.22	
3	150	15.00	15.01	100.07	

The UV-Visible spectrum of standard solution when compared with that of blank solution, there was no interference observed in the blank spectrum, indicates that the method was specific. The blank spectrum was shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Blank Spectrum

Limit of detection was found to be 10.56 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and limit of quantification was found to be 32.02 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, indicating the method to be sensitive.

IV. CONCLUSION

A simple, novel UV spectrophotometric method was developed for the determination of Nirmatrelvir in pharmaceutical dosage form and validated in accordance to ICH guidelines. The development method was found to be accurate, precise, linear, specific, and sensitive. This developed method can be easily applied for the estimation of Nirmatrelvir for routine analysis or for quality control in formulations.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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